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Abstract: Even after fifty years of freedom, the Christian community in India is still struggling to find an identity of its own in the country, and a constructive role in the nation building process. It finds itself at the centre of controversy time and again.¹ It is often attacked from without, and disunited from within. So this Golden Jubilee Year should be a time for introspection and reflection on its role in independent India. The author quotes M.M. Thomas perceptively : “The rights of religious minorities must be seen as coupled with the struggle for the rights of all minorities, regional, cultural, and most of all political ... It is sheer immaturity which concentrates on Christian minority rights without any reference to issues of civil liberties and democratic rights of all citizens.”

Keywords: Indian Christians, Christianity in India, Minority rights

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Christianity in Independent India

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Even after fifty years of freedom, the Christian community in India is still struggling to find an identity of its own in the country, and a constructive role in the nation building process. It finds itself at the centre of controversy time and again.¹ It is often attacked from without, and disunited from within. So this Golden Jubilee Year should be a time for introspection and reflection on its role in independent India.

There have been Christians in India for a long time, in fact, reaching back to the earliest period of Christianity. And yet, it is still a small minority religion, submerged within the culture of the dominant religions. This minority status still acts as a drag upon it, hampering it from taking up the challenge of opportunities that are peculiarly its own. It still views everything from a minority – which in practice means communal – perspective which leads to a feeling of insecurity and the urge to fight for its rights. This in turn has been exploited by successive governments who placated the Christians by protecting their communal rights in return for their political support. The Christian community has become a defensive rather than a creative minority.²

Christians are still uncomfortable about their colonial past, the association of their faith with the rather unedi-

fyng history of Christian nations in the west. It makes them introvert and estranged, in spite of the fact that they are engaged in a great deal of beneficial and worthwhile activities in different fields. Christians are still considered followers of a foreign religion, lacking in Indianness.³ They are still accused of converting others to their faith. In fact, the educational, medical and other institutions for humanitarian services that are run by Christians are seen as a ploy to conversion. There are Christians who still face discrimination because of their racial or social origins. Christians are still substantially dependent upon foreign funds to maintain their top-heavy institutions. The role of the Indian Christians in the political life of the country has been, by and large, inconspicuous. The majority of them come from the depressed classes.

What are the reasons for all these accusations? Have Christians, in the course of the last fifty years, contributed anything substantial to the Indian polity and national life? In attempting to answer these questions we have to go back to history, particularly the history of the National Movement and the Christian attitude towards it; we also have to examine the period immediately before independence and the Christian attitude to the events that transformed India from a colony to a sovereign na-

tion. By and large, Christians saw the National Movement as a Hindu movement, posing a threat to their identity. Only a few joined it actively, and as a result, the community faced a serious problem after independence, namely, the problem of integrating themselves in independent India. On the other hand, Christians were forthright in rejecting communal attitudes, separate electorates, reservations, the formation of a separate political party etc., and upheld the unity of the country which would protect the legitimate rights of all its citizens. They put complete trust in the common destiny of India and pledged to work for national integration; and this is acknowledged as their distinctive contribution in the framing of the Constitution of India. In the light of this pledge made by the Christian community to commit itself to the cause of national integration at the formation of free India, I would like to examine the self-understanding of the Indian Christians as a minority 'by compulsion', as one author has succinctly put it.⁴ It will also bring to light the truth of the accusations levelled against them by their fellow-citizens. Let us first of all, begin with a clarification of the term 'minority.'

1. The Concept of 'Minorities'

What is a minority? The term minority is a product of democracy. Democracy, based on majority rule, gives rise to the existence of dominated groups or minorities.⁵ The existence of minorities is based on a number of factors like race, culture, language, religion, economic functions, political functions etc. The minority-dominant

relationships are determined by variables of social, economic and political power which are unequally distributed between the two groups.⁶ A minority may have different aims, such as preservation of identity and culture on the basis of tolerance of differences and equality of opportunity; it may strive for assimilation and seek to lose its identity as a discrete group and try to merge with the dominant group; sometimes a minority may have secessionist aims like attainment of independence; or it may entertain militant aims to achieve political domination over the majority. Minorities are usually assigned a lower status in a given society in one or more of the four following areas of life: economic, political, legal and social. Sometimes minorities choose to exclude themselves voluntarily in order to protect their identity. Often minorities perform specialised functions in societies, like in the field of economics, politics, social life etc. The Sub-Commission on Prevention of Discrimination and Protection of Minorities set up under the Human Rights Commission defined minorities as including only those non-dominant groups in a population which possess and wish to preserve stable ethnic, religious or linguistic traditions or characteristics markedly different from those of the rest of the population and only those sufficient by themselves to develop these characteristics and loyal to the country of which they may be nationals.⁷ The Indian Constitution does not define minorities but recognises the existence of minorities and provides them with, apart from the fundamental rights, a special package of religious, educational and cultural

rights (articles 25-30); it has also created a constitutional machinery for safeguarding and implementing these rights. The three categories of minorities who can claim protection are minorities based on language, religion, and culture (articles 29-30). Accordingly, "Any section of citizens, being small in number in a definite area, in respect of religion, language or on any other ground, seeking equal or preferential treatment either to maintain its identity or to be assimilated with the majority is a minority."⁸ The concept of minority has nothing to do with number, but with an attitude of dominance and subservience in a given society.

The question of minorities is nowhere so pronounced as in India, particularly religious minorities, because in India religion plays an important role and its impact is very profound. The history of the origin of the various religions in India is outside the purview of this paper. However, the origin of the minority question, particularly during the British era, needs some exploring. First of all, the British effected the shift from minority consciousness to communal consciousness or minority communalism.⁹ This view is widely shared:

The Morely-Minto Reforms of 1909 gave political expression to the already latent social and religious divisions in the nation by the newly minted concept of communal representation. The classification of constituencies, under the Act of 1919 into general, special and reserved further consolidated these divisions; a process which was to give rise to what came to be known as the communal question and was to become the evil ge-

nius of Indian political life till its final exorcising by the creation of Pakistan.¹⁰

The British institutionalised division, hatred for one another and distinctions among communities, all for their convenience to rule and exploit this country. Religion was the best means to achieve this, considering the profound attachment of the people to religion. Separate electorates, separate family laws, caste quarrels, linguistic disorders etc. were created by them to divide the people. The terms minorities, communal etc. with their negative connotations were introduced by the British. British imperialism was never tired of doing anything to keep India divided, by pitching communities against one another. The minorities became unduly and unhealthily community conscious. After 1921, they acquired a sharp awareness that their interests were at stake and that necessary political action should be taken to safeguard them. The tendency began to emerge to emphasise differences, demanding undemocratic special privileges, concentrating on the narrow and selfish affairs of their own particular class, race or religion. Communal election plans were devised in order to perpetuate the hostility of religious communities among themselves.

Once the British had to leave and partition was a reality, India had to provide the minorities of the country adequate security so that such divisions might not be repeated, and to garner their support for the building up of the nation. This was the task of the founding fathers of the Constitution. Fears had to be removed from the hearts and minds of the Muslims, Christians,

Anglo-Indians, Sikhs, etc. On the eve of the drafting of the Constitution, India had 361 million people speaking about 845 languages or dialects with 15 major languages, belonging to Hindus, Muslims, Christians, Sikhs, Buddhists, Parsis and a small community of Jews; each of the minority groups had its own fears and suspicions.¹¹ In this paper I am concerned only with the Christian community and its attitudes.

Indian Christians played a minor, or rather insignificant, role in the creation of independent India. But once independence was a reality, they made a definite choice of joining the national mainstream of independent India by stating that they sought the protection of their cultural and religious identity not by separate electorates but by fundamental rights fortified by statutory safeguards. In this way they contributed to the founding of the democratic structure of the Indian society.¹² It was a manifestation of political maturity by the Christians. It was the result of a realisation among Christians that they do not have a destiny separate from that of other Indians, and the conviction that the task of the churches is not to fight for their own advantage, but to dedicate themselves to the common good. However, before we discuss that, a word must be said about the role of the Christians in the freedom struggle.

2. Indian Christians and the Struggle for Freedom

One hears accusations even today that Christians are anti-national because they did not take part actively in the freedom struggle. Perhaps history will shed some light upon the truth of these

accusations. However, this examination of history has to be content with general observations, because a definitive history of the role of the Christian community in the freedom struggle is yet to be written. Indian Christians belonging to the Roman Catholic and non-Catholic affiliations had different attitudes to the National Movement. It may be said with some certainty that generally Protestant Christians, particularly those who were not governed by an episcopal hierarchy had the most liberal attitude towards the National Movement; it was encouraged by a group of educated and enlightened people who found themselves under the canopy of the All India Conference of Indian Christians.¹³ Its leaders were committed nationalists. Catholics were confused about the response to the National Movement. "By contrast, the Catholics with a strong representation in the south and scattered in small communities in the north of India, encountered the changing political scenario, disunited, confused in their political thinking and falling back on episcopal directives for guidance in sorting out public issues – directives which, in the event, did not go beyond exhortations to guard the Catholic community from the encroachments of a wicked world..."¹⁴ For the Protestants, on the contrary, the All India Conference of Indian Christians founded in 1914 became the apex body for the expression of their political aspirations. Apart from its non-political objectives, the Conference wanted to formulate a common political policy in the wake of the National Movement and also wanted to join hands with the Roman Catholics to present a united front of the

Christians vis-à-vis the government. Already in the last decades of the 19th century, there were prominent Protestant Indian Christians who enthusiastically supported the Indian National Congress and attended its annual meetings.¹⁵

However, this participation slowly declined. According to G.A. Oddie, this decline of interest was due, on the one hand, to the evangelical view that individual salvation was more important than participation in mundane things such as politics; and on the other, the fear of being regarded as disloyal to the government; there was also the fear about the future, as to what would happen if the Congress and the nationalists achieved their objectives and India became an independent democracy dominated by a Hindu majority. The British authorities, too, began to look upon the activities of the Congress with suspicion, so also the western missionaries and the Indian Christians who were influenced by them. "Some Indian Christians therefore began to argue that it was extremely foolish to risk losing the support and favour of the British authorities through an association with what seemed to them to be an extremist organisation."¹⁶ Joseph J. Ghosh, a Bengali Christian writes in 1909:

We do not know in what way it will be of any advantage to Indian Christians if they join the non-Christians in political agitation. If further political rights and privileges are granted to the people of this country, our poor and small community will not have the remotest chance to be profited by them. On the other hand greater powers in the hands of non-Christians may prove

dangerous to the very life of our community. We know by experience that wherever the non-Christians are in power the poor Indian Christians labour under a great disadvantage and have to suffer humiliation, indignities and even persecution.¹⁷

K. M. Panikkar would later on say:

Christianity directly contributed but little to the growth of the nationalist feeling. The earlier of high caste converts, Kalipad Mukherji, Michael Madhusudan Dutt and Raja Harnam Singh remained nationally minded Indians even after their acceptance of Christianity; but with the growing estrangement between the British government, to which Christians as a community looked for encouragement, and the nationalist movement whose avowed object was to recover India's freedom, the Christian community found itself placed in a very difficult dilemma.¹⁸

Kaj Baago, the Protestant Church historian, speaks about the role of the National Christian Council in the National Movement in these words: "Prayer for peace was the repeated answer of the N.C.C. Review to the pressing political problems, and one cannot hold back the remark that the frequent calls to that issued from the N.C.C. in the years seem to have been just about the only contribution the Council found it possible to give to the nation's struggle for freedom."¹⁹ According to Baago, the main reason for the inability of the N.C.C. to give a lead to the Protestant Christian community in their struggle to respond to the national question was missionary influence and domination.

However, as the National Movement gained momentum, there were people who saw the damaging consequences of this position. C. F. Andrews said: "I cannot but feel that it should be the most serious blow to Indian Christianity if the impression gained ground that Indian Christians were opposed to the National Movement, and were only occupied in the interests of the their own community."²⁰ K. T. Paul, one of the most ardent nationalists would say:

We will do well to realise that there is a terrible danger if we persist in the policy of keeping aloof. Materially, socially, morally, and politically, viewed in fact from every standpoint, our interests are intimately bound up with those of other Indian communities. Will it ever be otherwise? Long after Britain's political mission to India is finished, let us hope five centuries later, for all things earthly must end or change – we shall still be Indians.²¹

Again,

What greater opportunity can arise than the crisis of today? ... To be born at this hour in India and to have the opportunity to take a share in the shaping of our national destinies at perhaps the most critical point of its history, if that is not an opportunity, what is? It would not only be a lamentable misapprehension of the spirit of Christ but also a grievous neglect of a great God-given opportunity, if it is not realised that Indian Christians have a tremendous duty in regard to the secular crisis in India.²²

However, the Resolutions of the All India Conference of Indian Christians in 1920 were still reserved in their attitude to the Indian National Congress

and the National Movement, in spite of the fact that there was already an emerging nationalist group in the Conference. It condemned the policy of non-cooperation as impractical, unwise, unnecessary and suicidal to the interests of the country. The policies of the Congress were considered to be in a state of flux. This was repeated in 1921. However, in the Conference of 1932-33, the situation changed and S. K. Dutta made an important contribution to the national cause by rejecting the government policy of dividing constituencies on a communal basis; but otherwise, he refused to change the Conference into a political body. He rejected separation and the devices of protection and said that the Christians were willing to assume their responsibilities as citizens of the country; but they would not accept the ignoring of the community's rightful aspirations:

We would announce once again to our countrymen that in the event of the abandonment of these devices of protection by the majority community, and the largest minority community, we are willing to take our place as citizens of the country. We are willing to work for a common Electoral Roll, open to all citizens, we are willing to abandon all these makings of separate communities, for places of power and prestige. Indeed it is our interest to do so, for our ambitions are greater than the narrow limits of our community. In the services for example, or in the Legislature, we do not desire our community to be marked with these percentages. In a community such as ours, an open field is the best incentive, and in the long run will pay us best.²³

In 1943 the Conference once again reaffirmed the commitment of the Christian community to the nationalist cause but pleaded for fair treatment from the majority communities:

We are behind no other community in our burning desire for a self-governing India in the immediate future. We are nationalists as much as any one else ... While we are Christians and proud to be such so far as our faith is concerned, in all other matters we are Indians first and Indians last. There is no antithesis between religion and patriotism, for a true Christian must be a good patriot. Indian Christians are ready to place their country above communal considerations ... Indian Christians wish to take their full share in the political and civic life of the country ... We should not forgo any opportunity of serving our country and through our country our community in being active members of legislatures, or in joining political associations, attending political meetings, and, above all, as a bridge community doing our utmost to narrow the gulf specially in times of communal tension between the two principal communities of India.²⁴

The Conference, however, said that if the government persisted in the view that communal considerations were still to be the basis for appointments, although the Christians were not in favour of that, they should also be given their due share.

The dilemma that the Catholic church faced was more excruciating. Led by bishops who were foreigners, and having their headquarters in a foreign country, it was difficult for her to understand how the Indian Catholics

could rise against a European power. The church realised the seriousness of the problem only in the period immediately before independence. Of course, there were some prominent nationalists among the Catholics already from the beginning of the National Movement, like Brahmabandab Upadhyay who, in his characteristic vitriolic style thundered against the British:

With the spread of English education and culture, India lost her own idea of civilisation. Our educated classes think as they have been taught by their *Firinghi* masters. Our minds have been conquered. We have become slaves. The faith in our own culture and the love for things Indian are gone. India will reach *Swaraj* the day she will again have faith in herself ... What we want is the emancipation of India. Our aim is that India may be free, that the stranger may be driven from our homes, that the continuity of the learning, the civilisation and the system of the *rishis* may be preserved ... Are we afraid of your cannons and guns? Arm brothers, arm! The day of deliverance is near. We have heard the voice and we cannot fail to see the chains of India removed before we die. It is now too late to recede.²⁵

Also the journals, *Light of the East*, and *The Week*, under the editorship of Aloysius Soares tried to keep the nationalist spirit alive in the minds of Catholics but they were voices crying in the wilderness of an apolitical community.²⁶ *The Week*, particularly, was uncompromisingly nationalist and rejected communal electorates, but at the same time found fault with Gandhi's political methods of non-cooperation and civil disobedience – a fact which

Gandhi deplored deeply. However, the hierarchy perceived its utterances as clearly 'uncatholic' and banned it from its colleges and seminaries. In the South, where the Catholics were more powerful than in the North, two associations claimed to represent the attitude of the people toward the National Movement: the Kanara Catholic Association of Mangalore, and the Catholic Association of South India centred on Madras. However, there was no clarity among the Catholics as to what was politics and what was religion, and what position had to be taken regarding the National Movement. They were divided according to regions, loyalties and ideologies. While separate electorates were vehemently supported by some, they were equally vehemently opposed by some others. No one body could claim to represent all the Catholics of the country. Some supported Gandhi while others rejected his methods. Some supported the Congress, while others saw it as a Hindu party. The Catholics were in absolute disarray.

Alfons Vāth, a Jesuit missionary who taught history at St. Xavier's College Mumbai, wrote that for Catholics, participation in the National Movement was an action against conscience because it was directed against a legally constituted government. They must remain loyal to the government and pursue their goals through lawful methods. He accused Gandhi of breaking the law and undermining respect for it; he said that he used morally objectionable methods for achieving his political ends. According to him, Gandhi and his companions did not possess the states-

manship to lead India to independence, and India did not have the necessary stature for becoming a nation. It possessed only geographical unity and not internal unity. It was not ready for independence.²⁷ According to him, Christians should reject the National Movement because it endangered missionary work. They needed neither full autonomy nor dominion status. They should show their gratitude to the British government which had been good to them. The National Movement was anti-European and anti-Christian. Even in 1946 the Catholic journal *Clergy Monthly* would deplore nationalism as endangering mission.²⁸ "Anyone who has eyes to see can realise that in India the present intense nationalism raises serious obstacles to the conversion work and contains unmistakable threats for the future."²⁹ It was considered unfavourable to the progress of Christianity by creating indifference, antagonism and prejudice. The surest way of being loyal to India was to be loyal to Christ and his church. The demand by Catholics for permission to cooperate with the Protestants in the struggle for freedom was disapproved by the hierarchy from the beginning. In 1920 many Catholics were present at the All India Conference of Indian Christians without ecclesiastical approval. In 1921, 1922 and 1923 there were no Catholic delegates present. Aloysius Soares, a prominent Catholic leader, lamented later the reasons for this attitude: "The fear and suspicion with which the Catholic Church looked at Reform churches in Europe – the fears were mutual – were imported into India by the white hierarchy and continued un-

abated till the last Vatican Council made the word ecumenism fashionable.”³⁰

However, in 1932, something positive happened in the Christian attitude towards the National Movement, namely, the creation of a common political platform for all the Christians of India, Roman Catholic and Protestant. At the Poona Conference of October 28, 1932, against opposition from many Catholics, it was affirmed also by the Catholics that separate electorates for Christians would be against their own interests. What they needed, rather, were religious and educational safeguards which would be part of the Fundamental Rights to be incorporated in a future Constitution of India.³¹ A copy of the Fundamental Rights as drawn up by the Conference was presented to the Prime Minister of Britain, but nothing came of it. In 1942, the arrival of the Cripps Mission made the matter of co-operation between the two churches still more urgent because it was felt that unless the Christians were organised, they would completely lose out on many fronts; the Protestant Christians invited the Catholics to respond to this challenge. Individual representatives responded to it but not the official church. In the meanwhile, realisation was growing among the Catholics of the need of an All India Catholic body. The result was the founding of the Catholic Union of India in 1944. After this, cooperation between the two bodies became easier. A Joint Committee of Catholics and Protestants was formed to salvage what was still possible and to assert their rights in the new India. Thus began the common efforts of the Indian Christians

to respond to the political challenges, practically on the eve of Independence.

3. Christian contribution to The Indian Constitution

To take part in the framing of the Constitution was one of the most crucial tasks faced by the Christians in independent India. As pointed out earlier, the most important concern of the Christians was the status of their religious Rights in independent India under a Hindu majority. Therefore, they demanded a strong Constitution with Fundamental rights which guarantee and safeguard religious freedom, including the right to propagate, together with their other legitimate rights. Already in February 1946 this demand was put before the Cabinet Mission by the Joint Committee of Catholics and Protestants. They wanted no special privileges for their community and were ready to accept joint electorates with or without reservation of seats. But they emphasised that religious minorities should have statutory protection for their religious and educational rights including the right to practise and propagate their religion.³² Later on this was fought for by the Christian representatives in the Constituent Assembly; it was opposed by many Hindu representatives on the ground that it would be a licence to convert people indiscriminately, and that it was against the secular character of the country.³³ Because of the strong leadership of Nehru and Patel, the article on religious freedom included also the right to propagate. I would like to briefly sketch the course of events that led to it.

4. The Constituent Assembly and Minority Rights³⁴

The Constituent Assembly met for the first time on 9 December 1946. It was composed of the representatives elected from the then elected legislative assemblies of the British Indian provinces, with the representatives of the princely states joining at a later stage. It was in no way a body elected on the basis of a liberal franchise. The nominees of the Indian National Congress were predominant, with a few members from other parties and a large number of independents. It had top intellectuals, distinguished jurists, and constitutional experts of the country from different religions, castes, various estates and interests, and a galaxy of freedom fighters. Of the total of 290 members who were eligible to attend, only 210 attended the meeting. The Muslim League was absent from the Constituent Assembly.

In the second meeting of the Constituent Assembly held on 13 December 1946, the procedure of providing constitutional safeguards to the minorities in India was taken up. A Resolution was adopted which had been passed at the Haripur Congress Session of 1938, which said that it was "its primary duty as well as its fundamental policy to protect the religious, linguistic, cultural and other rights of the minorities in India so as to assure for them in any scheme of government to which the Congress would be a party, the widest scope for their development and their participation in the fullest measure in the political, economic and cultural life of the nation."³⁵ This was welcomed by the representatives of the minority. On

29 January 1947, the Advisory Committee on the subject of Fundamental Rights, including rights of minorities, was set up and it met under the leadership of Sardar Patel on 27 February 1947. It set up the Subcommittees on Fundamental Rights and Minorities besides three other Subcommittees dealing with other national matters. The Subcommittee on Minorities was headed by H.C. Mukherji, the famous Christian leader from Bengal and it met on the same day. The question under consideration was how the economic, political, religious, educational and cultural interests of the minorities could be safeguarded; what should be the nature of the safeguards; how it could be ensured that these safeguards were effective and when they were to be eliminated.³⁶ Memoranda were submitted on behalf of the Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, Sikhs, and Anglo-Indians demanding constitutional safeguards. No specific communal safeguards were asked for on behalf of the Indian Christians and Parsis.

The Christian concern focused mainly on three clauses of the Draft Constitution drawn up by the Congress Party, which dominated the Constituent Assembly. They were clauses 13, 16 and 17 regarding the right to practise and propagate one's religion, religious instruction in aided schools, and the right to conversion from one religion to another. Clause 13 said that all persons are equally entitled to freedom of conscience and the right freely to profess, practise and propagate their religion subject to public order, morality or health and to the other provisions of this chapter. The question came up

before the Minority Rights Subcommittee on 26 March 1947. The words 'practise and propagate' aroused heated debates but the clause was passed by a majority vote. The clause also met with resistance at the Advisory Committee level. There, too, it was passed with a narrow majority and was incorporated into the Draft Constitution. At the General Assembly meeting of 1 May 1947 the Christians feared that it would not be passed without amendments but with the help of several prominent members who supported the clause it was passed. Fr. Jerome D'souza writing in retrospect speaks of the 'strong stand' taken by the Christian members in passing the entire clause.³⁷ This was a clause which granted religious freedom to the citizens of India in a manner not found in any other Constitution.

Clause 16 was regarding religious instruction in public schools. It said that those attending public schools receiving public funds shall not be compelled to take part in religious instruction that may be given there. This too was passed although after some debate. Clause 17 was regarding conversion. It said that conversion from one religion to another brought about by force or fraud or undue influence shall not be recognised by law. It created a lot of debate, particularly regarding the conversion of minors; there were many Hindus who clearly said that they were against all conversions from one religion to another because they feared that it would lead to another partition of the country. Fr. Jerome D'souza played a key role in the debate and said that the minorities did not need a better safeguard than clause 13; he also said that the way it

was discussed and adopted by the Constituent Assembly was very reassuring for the minorities.³⁸ The matter was referred to the Advisory Committee and the Christians suggested the following modifications: that conversion of minors with the consent of the parents be allowed; that conversions by fraud or force be banned; and that the words 'undue influence' be suppressed in the text. The Advisory Committee recommended that the entire clause concerning forced conversions and conversion of minors be omitted. The Constituent Assembly, which took up this matter after the solemnities of the first Independence Day, on 27 August 1947, accepted this proposal. The Christians showed themselves pleased with this decision. In general, the Christians were happy with the fact that the Fundamental Rights of minorities were accepted in the Constitution. In the words of Jerome D'souza:

If the Fundamental Rights, including as they do minority rights, are assured in an absolutely indubitable manner, no kind of political safeguards will be necessary for us and we shall not demand them, as long as, I say, this part of the Constitution is enforced without any kind of "encroachment" or misinterpretation ... As far as the small Christian community is concerned, we have gone a great way in giving up those political safeguards and we are prepared to go further and give up the reservations which have been made in certain provinces. And if we do so, it is because we know that in the spirit in which these fundamental rights have been guaranteed, there is for us an assurance of safety and a confidence which does not need to be propped up

or further affirmed by political safeguards and privileges.³⁹

In the session of 18 May 1949 the question of reservation of seats was discussed. Although separate electorates were given up, reservation of seats in joint electorates still existed. The Christian community readily accepted the abandonment of reservation. Fr. Jerome D'souza claimed that it was only in a spirit of compromise that reservation with joint electorates was accepted by the Christians. However, in the face of the completeness, the generosity, and the thoroughness with which individual rights have been safeguarded in the Fundamental Rights; the way in which these Fundamental Rights are placed under the power and jurisdiction of the Supreme Judicature; and the spirit in which these provisions were passed by the House, the Christians needed no reservation.

My main concern was with the safeguarding of fundamental rights and minority rights: right to profess, practise and propagate religion, to all citizens freedom of education, freedom of association etc. ... When these fundamental rights were made justiciable, that is when any violation of them by individuals or governments, could be challenged in a court of law, the Christians felt that the safeguard of preserving minority rights by reserving special seats for them in the Legislatures on the basis of their population, was no longer necessary and that in the interests of national integration it was best to merge with and become part of the general electorate.⁴⁰

In all this, the hope of the Christian members of the Constituent Assem-

bly was that their action was a great step in the direction of nation building, strengthening democracy and cooperation among the different communities of India. "In this way Muslims and Christians, Hindus and Parsis and Anglo-Indians, will stand shoulder to shoulder and work out the prosperity and happiness of all our people, and lead the new Democracy of India to the glorious triumphs which Providence assuredly has in store for her."⁴¹

Perhaps from a historical distance we can now appreciate the importance of this contribution. It is possible to go behind the motivations of the Christians in demanding the right to propagate their faith as a license to convert people to their faith indiscriminately. One cannot deny the fact that conversions have taken place with motivations other than religious, and still take place in isolated cases, not only to Christianity but also to other religions; it should be rejected as not in accordance with the spirit of any religion. However, from the quality of the interventions and appeals of the Christian representatives in the Constituent Assembly, it seems reasonable to conclude that they saw this right in a broader perspective, as fundamental to human freedom and as contributive to the strengthening of India's secular democracy rather than as a divisive factor. They believed that this would only enhance the freedom that India won in such a unique way. Therefore, we can say that it was a lasting contribution of the Christian community to the Constitution of India. The willingness of the Christians to give up separate electorates and reservations already at an early stage – one should say that this had to

happen sooner or later whether one liked it or not – was another far-sighted action.

5. Conclusion

However, one can only regret the fact that the Christian community soon seemed to have forgotten the implications of this pledge. Already the insistence by Christians on the right to propagate their religion was seen by some Indians as a communal attitude, although it is doubtful whether the Christians saw it from this perspective at that time. It was rather, happenings in the years after independence that made Christians become minority conscious, worried about their privileges and rights. The definition of the Scheduled Castes excluding Christians, thus bringing about problems for depressed class Christians; playing down the number of Christians in the 1951 Census; the questioning of the right to propagate religion by a number of Indians; the attitude of the government to missionaries; the appointment and functioning of the Niyogi Committee by the Madhya Pradesh government etc. sowed the seeds of fear in the minds of Christians.⁴² However, the strength of the Congress party and its government was able to allay their fears to a certain extent. A minority complex was, however, developing. In the post-Nehruvian era, there were still more events which were perceived as anti-Christian: the expulsion of missionaries from Assam; the general aversion to missionaries; the accusation that they were connected with foreign intelligence agencies and that conversion was going on in various parts of the country; the Freedom

of Religion bills introduced in state legislatures and even in Parliament; the regulations which were introduced regarding Christian educational institutions in various states etc. led to the emergence of a fresh wave of minority consciousness among the Christians. The Catholics demanded a Minorities Commission and some Christians even demanded separate electorates for Indian Christians. These were, however, rejected as an immature reaction.⁴³

During the emergency, the general attitude of the Christian churches, once again, was one of safeguarding minority rights; they participated in the 20 point programme of the government with little opposition to the oppressive measures of the Emergency, although several Christian individuals and groups did oppose the Emergency. M.M. Thomas branded the general attitude of the Christian community as “communal gratefulness,” which was contrary to the spirit of the gospel:

But the Church is more than a minority community concerned with its own communal interests. In Jesus Christ, it represents the humanity of all the people of India. From this angle, the Church's concern is with human rights, with justice and freedom for all people. Therefore communal gratefulness should not be carried to the point of betraying the Christian concern for the healthy development of the body politic.⁴⁴

In another place he expresses himself still more critically:

The church is not concerned with being the minority or majority, but with being the conscience and servant of all men and women as they seek their

social and spiritual well-being. The minority consciousness of the Indian Christian communities which makes them seek conformity to the powers that be because they promise protection to it, is a denial of the theological nature of the church of Jesus Christ.⁴⁵

During the Janata regime the Christian community was once again perturbed by the Arunachal Pradesh Freedom of Religion Bill and the alleged persecution of Christians there; then came the O.P. Tyagi Freedom of Religion Bill in Parliament supported by Morarji Desai. The churches reacted again and saw these developments as an assault upon their fundamental rights; there were others who saw this in a broader context of freedom for all citizens to follow their conscience. Recent governments have in no sense shown a marked shift in attitudes towards Christians or minorities.

But the dilemma seems clear to the Christians as to where to draw the line between minority rights and genuine participation in nation building. The tension is bound to persist, but the occasion of the celebration of the 50th year of free India may be an opportunity for some soul-searching; it is time to examine whether the pledge made by the founding fathers of the Constitution has been honoured. This pledge can be honoured by us only as genuine Christians and genuine Indians. The impli-

cations of this statement are many, and cannot be explicated here. However, this much can be said with certainty: on the eve of independence, Indian Christians showed themselves to be committed citizens of this country, ready to contribute their share toward the shaping of its destiny. This should be a matter of pride to them. They have done a great deal in honouring this commitment. Some developments in free India have instilled fear and insecurity in the minds of Christians regarding the secular credentials of the nation, particularly some happenings in recent times. However, that is no reason for going back on the pledge that we have made to the nation fifty years ago. Perhaps this is a historic opportunity, once again, to show the creative spirit of the Christian community to contribute to national integration and development while protecting its legitimate rights, as was done by the Christian community at the time of the framing of the Constitution. M. M. Thomas perceptively says: "The rights of religious minorities must be seen as coupled with the struggle for the rights of all minorities, regional, cultural, and most of all political ... It is sheer immaturity which concentrates on Christian minority rights without any reference to issues of civil liberties and democratic rights of all citizens."⁴⁶

Notes

1. Arun Shourie's book, *Missionaries in India: Continuities, Changes, Dilemmas*, New Delhi, ASA Publications, 1994, the issue of reservation for dalit Christians, the attack on priests and religious in different parts of the country etc. can be cited as examples.
2. G. Oommen, "Minority Consciousness of Christians in Post-Independence India: A Historical Perspective", *Indian Church History Review*, 19 (June, 1985), pp. 70-71.

3. M. Subhash, *Rights of Religious Minorities in India*, New Delhi, National Book Organization, 1988, p. 243.
4. *Ibid.*, p. 246.
5. *Ibid.*, pp. 1-20.
6. *Ibid.*, p. 3.
7. *Ibid.*, p. 8.
8. *Ibid.*, p. 10.
9. *Ibid.*, pp. 31-49.
10. C. Fonseca, "The Indian Christians and the Fundamental Rights", *Indian Church History Review*, 17 (December, 1983), p. 85.
11. M. Subhash, p. 53.
12. C. Fonseca, p. 87.
13. *Ibid.*, p. 86.
14. *Ibid.*
15. G. A. Oddie, "Indian Christians and the National Congress", *Indian Church History Review*, 2 (1968), pp. 45-54.
16. *Ibid.*, pp. 49-50.
17. Quoted in G. A. Oddie, p. 51.
18. K. M. Panikkar, *Foundations of New India*, London, Allen Unwin, 1963, p. 52.
19. T. V. Philip, "Protestant Christianity in India since 1858", in G. Menacherry, ed., *The St. Thomas Christian Encyclopedia of India*, v. 1, Trichur, 1982, p. 60.
20. *Ibid.*
21. G. A. Oddie, p. 52.
22. T. V. Philip, p. 60.
23. M. K. Kuriakose, *History of Christianity in India: Source Materials*, Madras, Christian Literature Society, p. 356.
24. *Ibid.*, p. 373.
25. *Ibid.*, pp. 268-270.
26. C. Fonseca, pp. 93-94.
27. I. Padinjarekuttu, *The Missionary Movement of the 19th and 20th Centuries and its Encounter with India*, Frankfurt am Main, Verlag Peter Lang, 1995, p. 137.
28. "Nationalism and the Missions", *Clergy Monthly*, 9 (1946), pp. 257-262.
29. *Ibid.*, p. 259.
30. C. Fonseca, p. 91.
31. *Ibid.*, p. 90.
32. *Ibid.*, p. 102.
33. G. Oommen, "Minority Consciousness of Christians...", pp. 55-56.
34. M. Subhash, pp. 52-82.
35. *Ibid.*, p. 56.
36. *Ibid.*, pp. 58ff.
37. L. Sundaram, *A Great Indian Jesuit: Fr. Jerome D'Souza*, Anand, Gujarat Sahitya Prakash, 1986, p. 165.
38. *Ibid.*, p. 167.

39. *Ibid.*, pp. 187-188.
40. *Ibid.*, p. 158.
41. *Ibid.*, p. 197.
42. G. Oommen, pp. 58-59.
43. *Ibid.*, pp. 61-64.
44. From a collection of reactions and responses by M. M. Thomas to the Emergency and the attitude of the Indian churches, *Religion and Society*, 24 (June & September, 1977), p. 217.
45. *Ibid.*, p. 243.
46. *Ibid.*, pp. 259-260.